

QUIZ

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FIRST NAME: Aka

PROGRAM CODE : DSDD

COURSE CODE : ACA-401D

PERIOD NUMBER: 6

INSTRUCTOR: Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. Plagiarism in academic writing describes the fact that:

- A writer cites the piece of work he or she is using within the actual text itself.
- A writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information.¹**
- An editor does not use UK or US spelling and punctuation consistently.
- A writer omits the date of the source inadvertently.

2. The aim of an academic essay is to:

- Persuade readers of an idea based on evidence.²**
- Discuss an idea that was not completed by a previous writer.

¹ Euclid University, "ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1," n.d., 9, accessed February 10, 2019, <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/>.

² Ibid., 2.

- Compile referential and bibliographic materials for future use.
 - Join two independent clauses, use a comma followed by a conjunction, a semicolon alone, or a semicolon followed by a sentence modifier.
3. **A research report differs from other kinds of persuasive writing in that it:**
- It is grounded on qualitative data exclusively.
 - It represents the simplest form of writing, with no binding rules.
 - Relates someone's personal story.
 - Rests on shared facts that readers accept as truths independent of the writer's feelings and beliefs.³**
4. **Primary sources derive from data:**
- Books and articles by other researchers.
 - Collected on source, such as laboratory results, survey or interview transcripts.⁴**
 - Advertising materials in published magazines.
 - Encyclopedias and dictionaries.
5. **Author-date style form is about:**
- Quoting the full bibliographic information of a source.

³ Kate L. Turabian, "A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers (8th Ed.)" (London: The University of Chicago Press, 2013), 15.

⁴ Ibid., 25.

- Organizing the bibliography based on chronological order of reference materials.
- Mentioning the author, the date and relevant page numbers.**⁵
- Indicating the type of the source clearly (article, book, etc.).

6. **Acronyms are abbreviations pronounced as:**

- A series of letters.
- A contracted form.
- None of the above.
- A single word.**⁶

7. **A qualitative methodological approach includes:**

- Exploring, discovering, understanding or developing a theory.**⁷
- Building knowledge on numerical data in order to confirm, contradict or test a theory.
- Using software to analyze quantities and measures.
- Basing the whole research paper on published academic works.

8. **The success and quality of data selection is dependent upon the relevance of research informants and appropriateness of data collection tools.**

⁵ Ibid., 88.

⁶ Ibid., 196.

⁷ Methodology Related Presentations – TCSPP, *Writing the Methodology Chapter of a Qualitative Study* by Philip Adu, Ph.D., YouTube Video, 2016, accessed August 11, 2019, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KRHvxY3N708>.

- True.**⁸
- False.
- Maybe.
- Cannot be determined.
9. **A quality research paper (dissertation or thesis) would resemble a connected piece, with each part:**
- Being divergent from the previous or following part.
- Standing alone, with no connection to elements prior to it, or succeeding it.
- Fitting in logically.**⁹
- Contradicting any other part.
10. **By way of illustration of the importance of punctuation in an academic paper, the European Commission Directorate-General for Translation (ECDGT) recommends using a comma to divide adjectives only if it is in the case of a series, like in:**
- “Stable, agricultural prices.”
- “Agricultural, moderate prices.”
- “Moderate, stable prices.”**¹⁰
- “Moderate, agricultural prices.”

⁸ Linda D. Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, “Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End” (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2008), 68–74.

⁹ Ibid., 166.

¹⁰ European Commission Directorate-General for Translation (ECDGT), “English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission,” July 2019, 16, accessed August 11, 2019, https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/styleguide_english_dgt_en.pdf.

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